

Ethics in Business: Transcending the Boundaries of Philosophy

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The issue of ethics in business is a universal phenomenon that is very challenging and has remained a troublesome cleft for every generation. This study focused on how ethics in business has transcended the boundaries of the discipline of philosophy so that it is not only an issue for theorizing and mere acquisition of knowledge for debates but for practical application for solutions to the issues of life. The data for this paper were mainly generated from secondary sources and few oral interviews. Ethics in business is beneficial to employees, leaders of business organizations, stakeholders, the environment and the society. The implementation of ethics in business projects the image and integrity of the organization, boosts productivity, sales and relationship with other business organization. There are implications for human and animal health and sustainability of the environment which makes ethics in business a germane sub-theme and a practice to be enforced. It transcends the discipline of philosophy and leverages an understanding of history, archaeology, biology, medicine among others, being value laden.

Keywords: Ethics, Business, Transcend, Boundaries and Philosophy.

INTRODUCTION

Ethics is of universal concern to all human beings irrespective of where they are located. Ethics, though a branch of the discipline of philosophy, it is so broad that it is linked with other areas of study such as anthropology, biology, economics, history, politics, sociology and theology. It is in this regard that the thrust of this discourse addresses ethics in business which is an aspect of economics as an academic discipline.

Ethical issues in business can often be difficult and challenging to the owner as some employees who should be accountable given the existence of laws and statutes that guide operations and their behaviour are not deterred from behaving unethically. Why then does one explain how ethics in business transcends the boundaries of philosophy? Which theories and approaches facilitate an understanding of the thrust of this discourse? What then are ethics and why are they important in business. These questions would guide further discussions on the subject matter.

What does the Term Ethics Mean?

Immanuel Kant believes that ethics consist of commands about what we ought to do and imperative or categorical imperative ethics refers to an absolute command (Kranak, 2019).

Ethics also refers to the discipline that deals with what is good and bad and with moral duty and obligations (Abiodun and Oyeniyi, 2014). From these definitions ethics broadly involves integrity, transparency, accountability, responsibility and fairness and these are attributes that should or ought to be exhibited in business activities and transactions. These attributes are critical because human beings are involved in producing needed goods and services for other citizens whose welfare should not be compromised and whose environment should not be degraded because of the need for sustainable development. Another dimension of Kant's exposition of ethics is that of morality in which he states

that moral rules are supposed to be universal laws.

Thus, such moral rules should apply to all people equally, irrespective of their needs. His notion of morality is stringent and demands that virtue is universal (CFI Team, 2015). More succinctly Kantian ethics are a set of universal moral principles that apply to all human beings, regardless of context or situation (CFI Team, 2015).

This means that ethical rules should be universal and following all persons. It also implies that all people deserve and should enjoy or experience equal moral consideration. Consequently, no person should be an exception irrespective of his/her situation. The idea of equality and in relation to ethics in business, the producer (business organisers and their products) and end users or consumers should benefit in the end, but not one group to be at a disadvantage position. The business should not thrive at the expense of stakeholders and consumers in the bid to amass properties and wealth. Rather it should feature greatest good for the greatest number, which introduces the idea of utilitarianism in business and commerce as would be further elucidated.

Why is Ethics Critical in Business?

The term Business refers to an organization or enterprising entity engaged in commercial, industrial, or professional activities that relate to and or involve some sort of economic production of goods or services and can be for-profit entities or non-profit organizations that fulfill a charitable mission or further a social cause (Hayes, A., 2023). Businesses vary in size, scope and specialization in terms of goods to be produced or regions to cover. As such there are sole proprietorships, large national and international corporations, small and medium scale enterprises, and so on. Business activities involve interaction between the workforce in the business organization, customers to be satisfied, productive tools and facilities, the environment where the organization is situated or located and the host communities.

Ethically, all these forces (human beings in particular) have to do what is right in the series of interactions, not compromising moral expectations for all those involved. Standards are cherished and expected as a sine-qua-non because they guide, direct and control behaviour among the forces of production, decisionmaking and commerce. Ethics also incorporates virtues, rights and obligations in the various interactions. It is the consumers obligation to provide feedback on the products and services they are provided.

It is the obligation of the business organization to provide and perform its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) without being prompted and due diligence in maintaining sustainable development of its environment of operation.

Also very important are virtues which refer to attitudes, dispositions or character traits that enable us to be and to

act in ways that develop this potential. They enable us to pursue the ideals we have adopted and they include honesty, courage, compassion, generosity, fidelity, integrity, fairness, self-control, prudence, respect, loyalty and transparency are all examples of virtues (Velasquez et al., 1988). Honesty in business is paramount especially in the use of scales and other measurement devices to sell different items/products to people. For example, one litre of honey, liquid soap, izal or any other disinfectant should be the same weight if re-measured. This is right, otherwise false measure becomes wrong and is dishonesty which is not ethical, but a deviation from the standard of behaviour accepted by the society. In the food industry ethics is paramount. A mixture of ingredients for preparing food by food vendors, restaurants, hotels and allied business organizations pose health risks if workers in these outfits do not do the right thing.

There are a plethora of unethical practices in business, such as deliberate violations or rules in industrial practices, tactics that take undue advantage of human weaknesses, abusive conduct, use of company's or organizational time for personal business; violating an organization's Cyber policies, such as surfing the internet during official hours, amongst others constitute unethical business practices. There are also several studies that have identified additional forms of unethical business and their causes. Some of these included: misleading advertising, production and use of substandard materials, boarding, diversion, overbilling, price collusion, tampering with customers' accounts, breach of trust, abuse of contractual specifications, illegal awards of contracts to cronies, petroleum products black marketeering (price hike and product adulteration), tax evasion, spam, bribes and inducements (Ayuba and Ibrahim, 2018). These unethical practices featured most in the manufacturing, banking, construction, telecommunication, automobile, transportation, oil and gas according to the study.

Some unethical practices in business relate to the employees, stakeholders and the leaders interaction and they include: nepotism which involves favouritism towards a family member or friends and this can occur during the employment process or during daily business operations. The implication is that the best suited and most deserving employee may not be hired and accorded the due recognition. Harassment and sexual harassment can be experienced by a male and/or a female employee. Sexual harassment refers to an undesired sexual behaviour that upsets an individual or offends, scares and humiliates the victim. It is usually an action that has not received due consent as such it is considered as a violent behaviour and for some persons, it makes them feel unsafe in that organization. It manifests in different ways such as unwanted sexual advances, sexual gestures, staring or suggestive looks and so on.

Harassment ordinarily involves regularly abusing,

assaulting or harming the victim. It ranges from teasing, undue criticism, among others. Similarly, the victims of harassment feel unsafe and emotionally disturbed which can negatively affect their labour output. Discrimination such as excluding an employee from a work schedule or event, team rendezvous, making fun of an individual, especially because of an aspect of his/her physical or emotional features or dressing and not giving an individual/employee the same training and promotion opportunities given to others are unethical practices that could negatively impact an employee's well-being and self-esteem (Papadopoulos, 2023).

Sometimes employees have knowledge of accumulated stocks for sale and buy them before the information is made public. This is an unethical practice known as „insider trading“, whereby the employees have an unfair advantage and are able to handle the shares for higher profits as they resell them. It is also possible that some of the employees might not resell the shares but hold on to them, grow them for more benefits in the future.

Causes of Unethical Practices in Business

Several reasons have been adduced for the occurrence of unethical behaviour in business. Peer influence for example, plays a major role because the individuals observe peers engaging in unethical practices or behaviour, the more likely they engage in similar behavior (Boes, 2015). In the construction industry inducements which are highly lucrative make employees to engage in unethical behaviour. This finding is replete in studies in Australia, Sweden, China, Ghana, India, Kenya, Nigeria, Malaysia, South Africa, amongst others. In construction and manufacturing industries employees are often under pressure to accept gifts in exchange for unethical practices and as top management staff indulges in this exchange, other staff members emulate them. This is an issue of setting a bad example (Maseko, 2017). Selfinterest, lack of empathy, pressure to meet targets or deadlines, poor or non-training of staff on company's codes of ethics as well as unclear company ethics are other factors.

Greed and pressure to succeed in business are major forces too. In Nigeria for example, many market men and women add Azo dye into palm oil to achieve a brighter red colour that attracts buyers. This dye stuff is carcinogenic and consumers of this adulterated palm oil suffer diverse organ damage/diseases of the liver, kidney and cancer of different parts of the body. Similarly, women use bleach and/or hypo or detergent to process cassava tubers into foo-foo. The end product is white and attracts buyers which enables them sell a lot in the day. Here, their interest is on aesthetics rather than on business ethics. Many women who process plantain chips that are hawked along the road in many Nigerian

cities and suburbs add cellophane (water proof) in the vegetable oil used for frying the chips in order to make them to remain strong. This reduces loss that would have resulted from breakages yet it is an unethical practice that affects human health (Gabriel, 2023).

Why Ethics in Business?

Ethics in business has many advantages which an organization should work hard to practice. For example, it can stimulate positive employee behaviour that creates positive ambiance in the company or organization. In this regard productivity is boosted as a result of employee improved and sustained performance and job satisfaction that contribute to the company's growth and development (Logne, 2013). Business organizations operate lawfully, safeguarding both employees and the general public when business ethics are practiced. Similarly, there is the establishment of a reputation for ethical behaviour when business organizations insist on ethics in their activities. In this way they gain trust in their products and services, attract investors, talented employees, retain their customers and their products and services gain wide recognition and growth (Twin, 2023).

Strategies for Implementing Business Ethics

Given the importance of ethics in business, it is also critical that all staff in a business organization should imbibe and implement business ethics as their leaders serve as role models. However, formal and informal training programmes on business ethics should be employed to harness and teach preferred values which would be aligned with organizational values. Each business organization should document its code of conduct or ethics, guiding principles, reporting procedures and ensure that employees imbibe them as they are enforced. A code of ethics encourages and sustains ethical conduct, even among peers. When these rules and regulations are strategically placed in some sections of the offices people unconsciously imbibe them as they move around every day. It is also necessary to inform staff of the consequences of indulging in unethical behaviours and these can be placed beside rules in such strategic places.

There are other strategies that some countries have adopted to promote ethics in business. In Ghana for example, three business Associations, namely the Ghana Employers Association, Association of Ghana Industries and the Ghana National Chamber of Commerce developed the first ever Ghana Business Code in 2006. The Ghana Business Code (GHBC) was modeled on the United Nations (UN) Global Compact with the aim of promoting ethics in business in the country (Fening et al., 2015). Despite the challenges of ethics in Business, there are students; ethical companies or organizations that

have attained high repute. For example, Accenture, a global professional services company provides consulting, technology and outsourcing solutions to various industries; Pepsico is a global food and beverage company that owns brands such as Pepsi, Frite-Lay, Quaker Oats, Gatorade, Tropicana, Doritos and Lays (Ozsevim, 2023).

Sterling Bank, Fidelity Bank and Dangote Cement were adjudged to uphold sustainable business practices and being best ethical companies in Nigeria by the analyst team of Askoraders (Asktraders, 2024). Sterling bank prevented credit card fraud and reduced its own carbon impact and so on. Fidelity bank strictly adhered to the international declaration of human rights, promoted financial inclusion, emancipation of women through establishment of an inclusive work environment and the elimination of negative environmental hazards. Dangote (cement) group adheres to ecologically friendly practices through "green growth". Staff are offered paid time off to improve on their education, work environment is risk-free and small and medium sized enterprises are granted aid.

Ethical Apparel Africa (EAA), established by Keren Pybus and Paloma Schackert partnered with three high potential factories in the Republic du Benin and Ghana that were committed to their workers and communities. In 2017, the company facilitated US \$350,000 in export orders (Business Call to Action, 2019). In order to entrench ethics in business, EAA provides training, generates orders, improves quality and increases efficiency of its partner factories workforces and supports factory managers to meet international standards. Also a portion of profits is reinvested into workforce well-being to cater for their living wages, healthcare, educational offerings and other benefits chosen by workers (Business Call to Action, 2019).

Transcending the Boundaries of Philosophy

Philosophy is a discipline - a set of thinking tools – that helps us to make better sense of the world around us. Thus, every time a person thinks about ideas, what they mean or how they fit together, the person reflects on values to help guide decisions and formulate an arguments, the person is doing philosophy (Dean, 2016). Philosophy is relevant to other disciplines such as history, medicine, education, archaeology, biology, engineering and other subjects. Ethics in particular transcends the boundaries of the knowledge of philosophy as a discipline. This area of applied ethics, therefore, is hydraheaded permeating the large spectrum of human endeavour as is subsequently discussed. Educational ethics addresses ethical issues related to the appropriate persons who should teach, how and what to teach according to the age and level of the pupils and in medical ethics a patient's privacy and confidentiality are to be respected and protected, while inappropriate

relationships with patients should not be engaged in; ethics of war respects the safety of civilians so that violent activities are not carried out where they are domiciled. Engineering ethics implies that the engineer should be conscious of his safety and those of others in any engineering projects he/she undertakes. For the historian, the quest for objectivity in historical reconstruction is necessary consequently different sources are employed in order to avoid bias in history writing. Again, an understanding of the values of the actors and the society in which events, activities and actions took place enables the historian to perform his craft. Ethical reasoning is inherent in human action and therefore essential to the explanation of historical acts, particularly as the actor's motivation guides his decision (Ahonon, 2023).

Archaeological ethics involves treating human remains with respect and dignity, excavating only what is needed for their study and interpretation as well as leaving parts of the sites not used for future research. Ethics in biology or bioethics is concerned with issues such as abortion, cloning, euthanasia among others. Consideration is whether it is right or wrong to engage in these activities. Several scholars, professionals, activists and so on have engaged on debates on these areas of concern but the fact remains that abortion can be undertaken in life threatening situations, euthanasia to reduce long waiting period for the total collapse of the body system for death to occur and cloning to bridge extinction of an animal species.

CONCLUSION

The core values of a society largely influences ethics in diverse endeavours people engage in and for this reason business ethics does not exist in a vacuum. In every clime, people value things being done in the right way and so there exist codes of ethics established not only by business organizations. Educational and health institutions among others have codes of ethics that govern the behaviour of their employees too. However, it is usual that in the society or business and other organizations there are persons who do not abide by rules and regulations of the organizations consequently it is not surprising that some business organizations engage in unethical practices and bear the negative consequences for such behaviour. Philosophy helps us understand values that we communicate in business and resolve conflicts that arise. Ethics elicit virtues such as transparency, honesty, respect, fairness, self-control, integrity, fidelity and so on that are critical to the development and sustainability of business.

Ethics in business is vital and transcends beyond the boundaries of philosophy. In this regard, it is vital for the development of human, animal and the society. The

greater good of everyone and the society is the greater good of all.

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